

BABUR AS A BRIGHT MANIFESTATION OF EASTERN LITERATURE

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Annotation: The article covers historical data about eastern literature and one of the most popular person, his life and creativity were discussed. On the other hand, article analyzes role of Bobur as a poet and king.

Key words: literary heritage, Baburid Empire, lyrical, quatrains, literary, scientific, memoir, "Baburname", unique copy, "Vakoyi-i-Baburi".

First of all, the great representative, the founder of dynasty Babur's, king and poet Zakhiriddin Bobur has a strong position in Uzbek literature. He had their role as a specialist in history, literature, and poet. In the second half of the twentieth century was the special phase in the history of Uzbek literature with its essence's summary compositional construction, artistic and illustrative way. In that phase, there were other poets also such as Zokhirjon Kholmuhammad's son Khabibiy, Sobir Abdulla, Nabikho,ja Nurillakho,ja's son Chustiy, Asgarali Charhiy, ErkinVahidov, Abdulla Aripov, Jamol Kamol who skilled in writing poetry. The several poets continued Alisher Navoi and Zakhiriddin Babur's works. They brought to their poem some mixtures of essences and weight from Navoi and Babur's ghazals.

February 14 is a special date in Uzbekistan. On this day, the great commander and ruler of the Baburid Empire, Zahiriddin Muhammad Bobur, was born. A famous great poet, who had a huge influence on Uzbek literature has left behind an invaluable literary heritage[1]. Bobur, the Timurid king who created the

Baburid Empire in India, was born in 1483 in the family of Timurid Prince Umarsheikh, the ruler of the Fergana region. At the age of 12, as a result of the tragic death of his father, he becomes the new ruler and enters into a fierce struggle for power in Transoxiana. In the period from 1494 to 1496, as a teenager, he participated in the battles for Samarkand and for the first time met on the battlefield with his strongest enemy – Sheibanikhan, who had a huge impact on the future of Babur. Babur managed to lay the foundation of the Baburid Empire in India, which lasted for about 300 years. Along with his military and political activities, Bobur was a great poet whose lyrical quatrains delight and inspire many people to this day. Babur was an acclaimed writer, who had a profound love for literature. His library was one of his most beloved possessions that he always carried around with him, and books were one of the treasures he searched for in new conquered lands[2]. In his memoirs, when he listed sovereigns and nobles of a conquered land, he also mentioned poets, musicians and other educated people. During his 47-year life, Babur left a rich literary and scientific heritage. He authored his famous memoir the [Bāburnāma](#), as well as beautiful lyrical works or [ghazals](#), treatises on Muslim jurisprudence (Mubayyin), poetics (Aruz risolasi), music, and a special [calligraphy](#), known as khatt-i Baburi.

He wrote one of the most famous oriental works in the literature world, Baburname. This is Babur's personal diaries, which he kept throughout his life, collected into one work by himself. The famous "Baburname" testifies to the history of the great Timurids, the struggle for the creation of great power. "Baburname" is not only a description of the author's personal life, but also a valuable source for studying the history, culture, life of people, and places visited by Bobur. The theme of the motherland occupies a special place in Babur's lyrics. In his poems, especially in the quatrains, longing for the motherland and boundless love for it are expressed with great impressive force. Among the scientific works of Babur "Treatise on aruz" is of particular importance; the work is devoted to the study of philological poetry foundations. "Baburname" is

considered rightly as the pinnacle of his creativity, a work which depicted historical events, outstanding personalities, and natural scenery. In addition, it is a kind of encyclopedia, containing scientific information on many aspects of life of that era. Also “Baburname” used tradition and other elements of folklore, is about descriptions of traditions and rituals.

Uzbek people are proud of the outstanding poet and brilliant scientist Babur’s masterpieces, which still are the link of cultural relations between the peoples of Central Asia, Afghanistan and India. In these countries, subject of hundreds of scientific and literary works, movies are dedicated to our ingenious countryman. The poet’s script works are kept in museums of France, Britain, the United States and other countries. For example, a unique copy of the work “Vakoyi-i-Baburi” was discovered in Iran, which includes “Mubayin”, a treatise on Islamic jurisprudence[3]. The manuscript, accompanied by commentary and a Persian translation, served as the object of further research as an example of calligraphy and book art. Unknown lists of Babur’s divans manuscript were previously found in the funds of Salar Jung Museum of Hyderabad (India). As a result of Uzbek and foreign scientists’ joint scientific and practical research, copies of the principal manuscripts of our illustrious ancestor’s works were delivered to Uzbekistan, so “Paris list of Babur’s divans”, album “Miniatures for “Baburname” – a winner at international book fairs, “Treatise on aruz” and many others were published here. Independence gave us unlimited opportunities to explore deeper and fuller precious facets of Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur’s creativity, to make his heritage a property of the international community.

Zakhiriddin Babur enrich Uzbek Aruz’s weight by the his “Aruz” brochure. One of such kind a lovely weight is hajazi musammani ashtar (weight and taq“te): foilun mafoiylun foilun mafoiylun – V – /V – – –/ – V – /V – – –. This weight belonging to hazaj bakhri is equal to foilun (– V –) in the branch of ashtar at the first and second quite weight of mafoiylun also equal to solim (V – – –) in the second and fourth weight. Alisher Navoi didn’t give any information about this

measure in his book “Mezonul avzon”. The first information about hazaji musammani ashtar is given at the “Treatise of Aruz” (“Mukhtasar”) which is written by the Babur. He acknowledged one thing in his works that he informed us “Mustam“ali matbu”. He counted this weight in the range of lovely measures. In that way, Bobur addressed to Jamiy and Khafiz then set his ghazals in a creative work of example from his own ghazals. Gofil olma ey soqiy, gul chogin ganimat tut, Vaqti aysh erur boqiy, ol chog,ir, ketur, bot tut [4]. Foilun – mafoiylun – foilun – mafoiylun (Ingrate don’t dye! Ey whine – server you know the heyday time as a valuable Time is amusement, so take a wine, in the transition of time). The given couplet is a philosophical theme and it was known as an only one selective poem written by Zakhiriddin Babur. Usually, according to Aruz rules, the poem's initial parts and couple bytes are written as the main measure. The single bytes are written an additional close to measures. The initial parts of the poem are written at hazaji musammani ashtar. The single byte of the fourth couplet was written hazaji musammani ashtari musabbagh: foilun mafoiylun foilun mafoiylun (– V – /V – – –/ – V – /V – – ~). This measure has not any independent, selective poem which was written by the Zakhiriddin Bobur.

In conclusion it should be noted that Babur also inherited a love for gardening, which was then a very popular pastime and craft. It was the tradition of Moghul princes to develop sites for recreation and pleasure during their lifetime and choose one of these as a last resting-place. So, Babur in his autobiography Baburnama, made will to be buried in the garden of his choice in Kabul, in a "grave, under the open sky, without any superstructure over it and without a gatekeeper". For this reason the Gardens of Babur were built with the tomb of the Emperor, the founder of the Baburid dynasty.

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